

FACTORS AFFECTING VENTILATOR ASSOCIATED PNEUMONIA IN A PAEDIATRIC INTENSIVE CARE UNIT

Badurunisha Meerasa, Arulraj Russelian, Poornima M, Rajashree GR,

Department of Paediatrics, Bharath Medical College and Hospital, Chennai -
600073

Corresponding Author - Badurunisha Meerasa

Received: Dec 25, 2025

Accepted: Jan 21, 2026

Published: Jan 24, 2026

ABSTRACT

Background:

Ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) is a common and serious nosocomial infection in paediatric intensive care units (PICUs), contributing to increased morbidity, mortality, and healthcare burden. Early identification of risk factors and outcome predictors is essential to improve patient outcomes.

Objectives:

To determine the prevalence of ventilator-associated pneumonia in a tertiary-care PICU, analyze the clinical and microbiological profile, identify factors associated with mortality, and evaluate independent predictors of adverse outcomes.

Methods:

This cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted in the PICU of a tertiary-care hospital from July 2022 to June 2023. Children aged 1 month to 12 years who required mechanical ventilation for more than 48 hours were included. VAP was diagnosed based on clinical, laboratory, and radiological criteria. Endotracheal aspirates were cultured for microbiological analysis. Statistical analysis included univariate and multivariate logistic regression to identify predictors of mortality.

Results :

Of 232 mechanically ventilated children, 42 developed VAP, yielding a prevalence of 22%. The mean age was 3.12, and VAP was diagnosed at a mean of 4.21 ± 1.16 days after intubation. Gram-negative organisms predominated, with *Acinetobacter* species being the most common isolate (47.6%). Overall mortality among VAP patients was 40.5%. On multivariate analysis, leukocyte count $>11,000/\text{mm}^3$, radiographic infiltrates, reintubation, and abnormal temperature were independent predictors of mortality.

Conclusion:

Ventilator-associated pneumonia remains a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in the PICU. Early identification of high-risk patients and strict implementation of preventive strategies are crucial to improving outcomes.

Keywords:

Ventilator-associated pneumonia, Leucocytosis, Reintubation, *Acinetobacter*

INTRODUCTION

Ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) is defined as pneumonia that develops 48 hours or more after endotracheal intubation and initiation of mechanical ventilation. It remains one of the most important hospital-acquired infections in paediatric intensive care units (PICUs) and is second only to catheter-associated infections in terms of frequency [1]. VAP contributes significantly to increased morbidity, mortality, prolonged duration of mechanical ventilation, extended length of PICU stay, escalation of healthcare costs, and excessive use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, thereby promoting antimicrobial resistance [2].

The reported incidence of VAP in children varies widely across studies, ranging from 2% to 35%, depending on diagnostic criteria, patient population, surveillance methodology, and infection control practices [3,4]. Mortality associated with paediatric VAP has been reported to range from 20% to as high

as 70% in high-risk groups, particularly in those with underlying co-morbidities and infection with multidrug-resistant organisms [5].

Children are uniquely vulnerable to VAP due to age-related anatomical and physiological characteristics such as smaller airway caliber, immature immune response, reduced functional residual capacity, and limited pulmonary reserve [6]. Diagnostic challenges are also greater in children, as clinical signs such as fever, leukocytosis, and radiological infiltrates may overlap with other conditions including acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), pulmonary edema, atelectasis, or primary lung disease [7].

The pathogenesis of VAP is multifactorial. The primary mechanism is micro aspiration of colonised oropharyngeal and gastric secretions around the endotracheal tube cuff, facilitated by bypassing of natural airway defences and stenting open of the vocal cords [8]. This risk is compounded by impaired mucociliary clearance, suppression of cough reflex due to sedation, frequent airway manipulation, and prolonged duration of ventilation [9]. Biofilm formation on the inner surface of endotracheal tubes plays a pivotal role by acting as a persistent reservoir of pathogens and conferring up to a 1,000-fold increase in resistance to antimicrobial agents [10].

Ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI), through mechanisms such as barotrauma, volutrauma, atelectrauma, and biotrauma, further predisposes ventilated children to secondary infections by disrupting alveolar-capillary integrity and amplifying inflammatory responses [11].

Given the significant clinical impact of VAP and the paucity of regionspecific paediatric data, especially from resource-limited settings, this study was undertaken to estimate the prevalence of VAP in a tertiary-care PICU, identify microbial etiological agents, analyze associated clinical and laboratory risk factors, and determine predictors of mortality.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting: This cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted in the Paediatric Intensive Care Unit of the Department of Paediatrics at a tertiary referral centre catering to critically ill children from urban and rural regions of South India.

Study Period: The study was carried out over a one-year period from July 2022 to June 2023. The institute ethical clearance was obtained prior to the commencement of the study.

Study Population: Children aged between 1 month and 12 years who were admitted to the PICU and required mechanical ventilation for more than 48 hours during the study period were screened for inclusion.

Inclusion Criteria: Children undergoing mechanical ventilation for more than 48 hours with clinical and radiological evidence suggestive of ventilator-associated pneumonia were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Children with pneumonia prior to initiation of mechanical ventilation or within the first 48 hours of ventilation were excluded. Patients with severe immunocompromised states such as acquired immunodeficiency syndrome, post-organ transplantation, or terminal malignancy were also excluded to avoid confounding effects.

Methodology: All ventilated children were prospectively monitored for clinical features suggestive of VAP. A partial septic screen including complete blood count and C-reactive protein (CRP) was performed in suspected cases. VAP was diagnosed when a child ventilated for more than 48 hours developed at least two of the following criteria: fever $\geq 38.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ or hypothermia $\leq 36^{\circ}\text{C}$, total leukocyte count $< 4,000/\text{mm}^3$ or $> 11,000/\text{mm}^3$, positive CRP, and new or progressive infiltrates on chest radiograph [12]. Chest radiographs were interpreted by the same Paediatrician and compared with pre-intubation films to identify progression of infiltrates. Endotracheal tube aspirates were collected under strict aseptic precautions and sent for microbiological culture. All patients were managed according to institutional ventilator care bundles, including head-

end elevation, oral hygiene, sedation protocols, and daily assessment for weaning [13].

Statistical Analysis: Data was entered into a structured proforma and analyzed using SPSSv25 (IBM Corp., NY., USA). Descriptive statistics were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation or percentages as appropriate. Associations between categorical variables and mortality were assessed using chi-square or Fisher's exact test. Logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent predictors of mortality, and p-values <0.05 were considered statistically significant.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

A total of 232 children required mechanical ventilation for more than 48 hours during the study period. Of these, 42 children fulfilled diagnostic criteria for VAP, resulting in a prevalence of 22%.

Variable	Value
Total ventilated patients	232
VAP cases	42
Prevalence of VAP	22%
Mean age (years)	3.12
Age range	0.1 – 11 years
Mean day of VAP diagnosis	4.21 \pm 1.16
Mean duration of intubation	8.31 \pm 3.05 days
Male	66.7%
Female	33.3%

Table 1 - Prevalence and baseline characteristics

As seen in Table 1, the mean age of children who developed VAP was 3.12 years, with ages ranging from 1 month to 11 years. VAP was diagnosed at

a mean of 4.21 ± 1.16 days after initiation of mechanical ventilation. The mean duration of intubation among VAP cases was 8.31 ± 3.05 days. There was a male predominance, with 66.7% males and 33.3% females. The most common primary diagnosis among children who developed VAP was central nervous system infection (40.5%), followed by pneumonia (19%) and metabolic disorders (14.3%).

Parameter	Percentage
Pre-intubation diffuse infiltrates on X-ray	57.1
Radiological progression after intubation	100
CRP positive	95.2
Leukocyte count $>11,000/\text{mm}^3$	76.2
Purulent tracheal secretions	64.3
Reintubation required	59.5
Hypothermia / Hyperthermia	45.2

Table 2 - Clinical, Laboratory, and Radiological Profile

As seen in Table 2, More than half of the children (57.1%) had diffuse infiltrates on chest X-ray prior to intubation, and all children (100%) showed radiographic progression after 48 hours of mechanical ventilation. Inflammatory markers were frequently abnormal, with CRP positivity in 95.2% and leukocyte count $>11,000/\text{mm}^3$ in 76.2% of cases. Clinically, purulent tracheal secretions were noted in 64.3% of children. Reintubation was required in 59.5% of cases, and hypothermia or hyperthermia was observed in 45.2%.

Organism	Percentage
Acinetobacter spp.	47.6
Klebsiella spp.	21.4
Pseudomonas	4.8
aeruginosa	

Escherichia coli	2.4
No growth	23.8

Table 3 - Microbiological Profile of Endotracheal Aspirate Cultures

As seen in Table 3, Endotracheal aspirate cultures were positive in 76.2% of children with VAP. Acinetobacter species were the most commonly isolated organisms (47.6%), followed by Klebsiella species (21.4%). Other organisms included Pseudomonas aeruginosa (4.8%) and Escherichia coli (2.4%). No growth was observed in 23.8% of samples.

Variable	Mortality (%)	p value
Overall mortality	40.5	–
Pre-intubation X-ray infiltrates	53.6	0.014
Leukocyte count >11,000/mm ³	50.0	0.031
Reintubation	56.0	0.013
Hypothermia / Hyperthermia	63.2	0.006

Table 4 - Outcome and Univariate Association with Mortality

As seen in Table 4, overall mortality rate among children with VAP was 40.5%. On univariate analysis, mortality was significantly higher in children with pre-intubation chest X-ray infiltrates, leukocyte count >11,000/mm³, reintubation, and abnormal temperature (hypo/hyperthermia). There was no statistically significant association between mortality and sex, referral status, CRP positivity, steroid use, sedative use, vaccination status, or use of H2 blockers/proton pump inhibitors.

Variable	Adjusted Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p value
Leukocyte count >11,000/mm ³	180.3 (3.5 – 9235.7)	0.010
X-ray infiltrates	14.5 (1.09 – 192.1)	0.043
Reintubation	15.98 (1.30 – 196.2)	0.030
Hypothermia / Hyperthermia	24.43 (1.38 – 431.5)	0.029

Table 5 - Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis for Predictors of Mortality

As seen in Table 5, multivariate logistic regression analysis, leukocyte count >11,000/mm³, presence of radiographic infiltrates, reintubation, and abnormal temperature emerged as independent predictors of mortality.

DISCUSSION

The present study demonstrates a VAP prevalence of 22%, which aligns with reported rates from Indian PICUs ranging between 20% and 27% [3, 4]. The persistence of high VAP rates despite bundle implementation underscores the complexity of prevention in critically ill children.

Male predominance observed in this cohort is consistent with previous studies and may reflect higher PICU admission rates rather than true biological susceptibility [14]. VAP occurred at a mean of 4.2 days following intubation, highlighting the vulnerability during the early ventilation period, as emphasized by older studies [15].

Reintubation emerged as a strong independent predictor of mortality. Radiographic infiltrates prior to intubation were also associated with increased mortality, suggesting that underlying lung pathology worsens outcomes once VAP develops. This is similar to a study done in 2006 [8].

Leukocytosis (>11,000/mm³) was the most powerful predictor of mortality, remaining significant in multivariate analysis. Similar observations

were reported in a 2021 case report [16], who highlighted the prognostic utility of hematological markers in VAP severity assessment.

The predominance of *Acinetobacter* and *Klebsiella* species reflects the increasing burden of multidrug-resistant gram-negative organisms in PICUs, particularly in developing countries comparable to older studies [17].

Temperature extremes were significantly associated with mortality, reflecting systemic inflammatory response and sepsis-related dysregulation, consistent with observations by a 2022 study [18]. In contrast, steroid use, sedative exposure, and acid-suppressive therapy did not show significant associations with mortality, echoing mixed evidence in existing literature [19, 20].

CONCLUSION

Ventilator-associated pneumonia remains a major cause of morbidity and mortality in paediatric intensive care units. This study reports a VAP prevalence of 22% with a mortality rate of 40.5%. Independent predictors of mortality included leukocytosis, radiographic infiltrates, reintubation, and abnormal temperature. Gram-negative organisms, particularly *Acinetobacter*, were the predominant pathogens. Early identification of high-risk patients, strict adherence to preventive bundles, minimization of reintubation, and robust antimicrobial stewardship are essential to improve outcomes in ventilated children.

LIMITATIONS

This single-centre study with a relatively small sample size limits generalizability. Antibiotic sensitivity patterns and severity scoring systems were not included. Advanced biomarkers such as procalcitonin and microbiome analysis were not evaluated. Multicentric prospective studies are required to validate these findings.

Conflict of interest: Nil.

Funding: Nil.

REFERENCES

1. Foglia E, Meier MD, Elward A. Ventilator-associated pneumonia in neonatal and pediatric intensive care unit patients. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2007;20(3):409-425.
2. Klompas M, Branson R, Cawcutt K et al. Strategies to prevent ventilator-associated pneumonia, ventilator-associated events, and nonventilator hospital-acquired pneumonia in acute-care hospitals: 2022 Update. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiol.* 2022;43(6):687-713.
3. Vijay G, Mandal A, Sankar J, Kapil A, Lodha R, Kabra SK. Ventilator Associated Pneumonia in Pediatric Intensive Care Unit: Incidence, Risk Factors and Etiological Agents. *Indian J Pediatr.* 2018 Oct;85(10):861-866.
4. Awasthi S, Tahazzul M, Ambast A, Govil YC, Jain A. Longer duration of mechanical ventilation was found to be associated with ventilator-associated pneumonia in children aged 1 month to 12 years in India. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2013;66(1):62-66.
5. Pen DL, Yan GF, He LY, et al. The role of bacterial colonization of ventilator circuit in development of ventilator-associated pneumonia: a prospective observational cohort study. *Clin Microbiol Infect.* 2021;27(3):467.e1-467.e7.
6. Nelson Textbook of Pediatrics. 21st ed. Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier Inc.; 2020. ISBN 9780323568883. Available online via Elsevier Elibrary.
7. Kalamitsou S, Violaki A, Iosifidis E, Avramidou V, et al. Ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP) in children: a diagnostic challenge. *Signa Vitae.* 2023. 19(4):6-19.
8. Koenig SM, Truwit JD. Ventilator-associated pneumonia: diagnosis, treatment, and prevention. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2006;19(4):637-657.
9. Ericson JE, McGuire J, Michaels MG, Schwarz A, Frenck R, Deville JG, et al. Best Pharmaceuticals for Children Act—Pediatric Trials Network Steering Committee and the Clinical Trials Transformation Initiative. Hospital-acquired Pneumonia and Ventilator-associated Pneumonia in Children: A Prospective Natural History and Case-Control Study. *Pediatr Infect Dis J.* 2020 Aug;39(8):658-664.

10. Sharma S, Mohler J, Mahajan SD, Schwartz SA, Bruggemann L, Aalinkeel R. Microbial Biofilm: A Review on Formation, Infection, Antibiotic Resistance, Control Measures, and Innovative Treatment. *Microorganisms*. 2023;11(6):1614.
11. Silva PL, Scharffenberg M, Rocco PRM. Understanding the mechanisms of ventilator-induced lung injury using animal models. *Intensive Care Med Exp*. 2023 Nov 27;11(1):82.
12. Sachdev A, Chugh K, Sethi M, Gupta D, Wattal C, Menon G. Diagnosis of ventilator-associated pneumonia in children in resource-limited setting: a comparative study of bronchoscopic and nonbronchoscopic methods. *Pediatr Crit Care Med*. 2010;11(2):258-266.
13. Narang S. Use of ventilator bundle to prevent ventilator associated pneumonia. *Oman Med J*. 2008;23(2):96-99.
14. Kumar AK, Singh SN, Singh VK, Sharma B, Tiwari HC. Incidence and outcomes of ventilator associated pneumonia in pediatric patients: an observational study . *International Journal of Contemporary Pediatrics* 2024; 11(6), 752–756.
15. Gunalan A, Sastry AS, Ramanathan V, Sistla S. Early- vs Late-onset Ventilator-associated Pneumonia in Critically Ill Adults: Comparison of Risk Factors, Outcome, and Microbial Profile. *Indian J Crit Care Med*. 2023;27(6):411-415.
16. Maniara BP, Wells I. Ceftolozane/Tazobactam-Induced Leukocytosis and Clinical Failure in a Patient Being Treated for Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia Caused by Carbapenem-Resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: a Case Report. *SN Compr Clin Med*. 2021;3(2):701-704.
17. Rosenthal VD, Duszynska W, Ider BE, et al. International Nosocomial Infection Control Consortium (INICC) report, data summary of 45 countries for 2013-2018, Adult and Pediatric Units, Device-associated Module. *Am J Infect Control*. 2021;49(10):1267-1274.
18. Klompas M, Branson R, Cawcutt K, et al. Strategies to prevent ventilator-associated pneumonia, ventilator-associated events, and nonventilator hospital-acquired pneumonia in acute-care hospitals: 2022 Update. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiol*. 2022;43(6):687-713.
19. Lamouche-Wilquin P, Souchard J, Pere M, et al. Early steroids and ventilator-associated pneumonia in COVID-19-related ARDS. *Crit Care*. 2022;26(1):233.

20. Hernandez-Garcia M, Girona-Alarcon M, Bobillo-Perez S, et al. Ventilator-associated pneumonia is linked to a worse prognosis than community-acquired pneumonia in children. PLoS One. 2022;17(7):e0271450.